

Asset Master Data Management: Ensuring Accuracy and Consistency in Industrial Operations

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Abstract—The problems of data quality are topical nowadays, and the tendencies of growing amounts of data bring certain challenges to data management strategies. Also, technical tools of today allow for data that is more than most firms can administrate and different business solutions can result in increased data density. Master data management is truly experiencing globalisation at an exponential rate because its relevance or a link to the results or income does not have a direct connection to the operation of an organisation. In the contemporary world that is characterised by stiff economy competition, proper management of master data is crucial to making right strategic decisions and management of an organisation for efficient functioning. This paper aims at studying the topic of Master Data Management (MDM) taking into account the enhancement of dependability, consistency and quality of numerous fields of activity. Focusing on a single scheme of Master Data Management and the integration of various data sources, it describes MDM frameworks and implementation methods. The study reviews different types of MDM solutions—operational, analytic, and enterprise—and discusses key phases and approaches for successful MDM implementation. Furthermore, it investigates current research trends and gaps in MDM literature, highlighting the need for adaptive and scalable MDM architectures tailored to evolving organizational needs.

Keywords—Asset, Data Management, Master Data Management, Styles Implementation, Challenges, Benefit.

I. INTRODUCTION

Organisations must have trustworthy information system governance in place to keep up with the ever-changing IT landscape. Reliable and trustworthy information systems are essential for supporting business choices and laying the groundwork for future organizational development by ensuring data quality, consistency, and correctness.

Data is a valuable asset controlled by an organisation. Many organisations struggle with data management because it is controlled separately by several functional and structural groups. There are variances in the data formats utilised by different parts of the organisation, resulting in data consistency. If data is properly handled, it will generate information that the organisation can utilise to make decisions.

Increasing the volume of data poses a difficulty for organisational data management. It produces data quality difficulties, which are quite widespread in today's organisations. Data quality is a significant issue for organisations with information systems spread across several units or departments.

Data quality issues, like inconsistency and duplication, may be addressed with the use of such information systems. Hopefully, these issues will be lessened with the help of master data management (MDM) [1][2].

Effective data management becomes essential for success in the highly competitive industrial sector. Master Data Management (MDM) is becoming an essential practice for manufacturers all over the world as it is recognised as a critical cornerstone in guaranteeing data correctness, consistency, and reliability. The concept of MDM is introduced in this part, with a focus on its critical function in the manufacturing industry. Fundamentally, MDM is a methodical way to manage the most important data assets inside an organisation. These resources, which are sometimes referred to as "master data," include basic data such as product characteristics, supplier information, customer information, and personnel records that support different aspects of manufacturing processes[3][4].

Figure 1: Master data management framework

Figure 1 illustrates the framework that is used in Master data management, which delineates how essential data components could be standardised, recorded, supervised, and updated by the company across the enterprise[5].

The manufacturing industry is significantly dependent on precise and trustworthy information for all of its many processes. MDM guarantees the consistency and timeliness of product specifications, engineering drawings, and bill of materials throughout the product design process. During production[6][7], MDM ensures that production instructions and product configurations are maintained accurately, which lowers errors and improves quality control. MDM is essential to SCM since it helps with inventory monitoring and management, supplier interactions, and procurement procedures, all of which promote successful and economical operations [8]. Moreover, MDM guarantees the confidentiality and quality of customer data in today's customer-centric manufacturing environment, enabling tailored interactions and fostering brand trust [2][9].

The motivation behind this paper lies in addressing critical challenges faced by manufacturing organisations in managing vast and diverse datasets. With the proliferation of data sources and formats across various operational units, maintaining data quality, consistency, and accuracy becomes increasingly complex. MDM emerges as a pivotal solution, aiming to streamline data governance and integration processes. By providing a conceptual framework, categorising MDM types, and analysing implementation strategies, this study seeks to equip manufacturing leaders with actionable insights to enhance operational efficiency, decision-making accuracy, and overall competitiveness. The significance of this research lies in its potential to foster better data-driven strategies and optimise resource allocation, ultimately driving organisational growth and resilience in today's data-intensive manufacturing landscape. Based on the work, here are five key contributions of the paper:

- The paper contributes by presenting a comprehensive conceptual framework of MDM within the manufacturing sector. It defines MDM and outlines its crucial role in ensuring data quality, consistency, and reliability across various operational domains.
- It categorises and discusses different types of MDM solutions—operational, analytic, and enterprise—providing insights into their functionalities and benefits. The paper also explores key implementation phases and strategies essential for successful MDM deployment.
- The study emphasises the importance of integrating disparate data sources through MDM frameworks. It highlights how MDM facilitates the creation of a unified, authoritative source of master data, crucial for enhancing operational efficiency and decision-making accuracy in manufacturing.
- It contributes by reviewing current research trends and identifying gaps in MDM literature, particularly in areas such as open-source MDM solutions, cybersecurity integration, and adaptive MDM architectures. This analysis sets the stage for future advancements in MDM practices and frameworks.
- The paper presents practical insights from industry executives through interviews, discussing challenges faced and strategies adopted in MDM implementation. These insights enrich the understanding of real-world applications and challenges of MDM in manufacturing settings.

A. Structure of the paper

This is the arrangement of the remaining paper. In Section 2, an overview of asset master data management is presented, including its definition and domain within organisational

contexts. Section 3 outlines the phases, types, and approaches of master data management (MDM). Section 4 explores various practices for implementing MDM specifically tailored to the manufacturing sector. Section 5 examines the application of MDM principles within the healthcare industry. Section 6 conducts a comprehensive literature review to synthesise existing research on MDM across different sectors. Finally, Section 7 consolidates the findings and insights from the study, providing a conclusive summary of the work.

II. OVERVIEW OF ASSET MASTER DATA MANAGEMENT

Data from many departments within an organisation, including sales, service, order management, production, purchasing, billing, accounts receivable, and accounts payable, interact and connect to form business intelligence (BI) systems [10]. Information that is deemed crucial to the fundamental functioning of a company, often shared by several users and organisations within the company and kept on various systems, is referred to as master data, which is also known as reference data [11][12][13]. Master Data is a great way to get dimensional data and works well with BI. The information, characteristics, definitions, roles, relationships, and taxonomies that accompany data objects used in various applications within the organisation are referred to as master data. Master data is information that has been standardised, cleansed, and incorporated into an enterprise-wide system after being used in a variety of business areas[14] [15][16]. All organisations, customers, prospects, residents, workers, vendors, suppliers, and trade partners are considered core entities. So are locations, offices, regional alignments, and accounting records, assets, policies, and products and services[17][18].

There are essentially five types of data in corporations:

- **Unstructured**— The following sources include this information: PDF files, marketing materials, product specs, white papers, magazine articles, corporate intranet portals, and electronic mail.
- **Transactional**— This information pertains to claims, sales, orders, invoices, and entries.
- **Metadata**— It pertains to information stored in a data warehouse. It may be in a repository or it might be in a variety of different formats, such XML documents, report definitions, or log file data column descriptions.
- **Hierarchical**— Data that is organised hierarchically keeps track of the connections between different types of data. Information on actual relationships, such those between product lines or firm hierarchies, may be kept in a separate database.
- **Master**: The four main types of master data, which are people, things, locations, and concepts, are essential to company operations. In addition, groupings are created based on entity types, subject areas, and domain areas. Customers, employees, and third-party staff are examples of the many types of people. Products, stores, commodities, and assets are all included inside objects. Things like agreements, warranties, and licenses are included inside conceptions. Lastly, there are sites, office locations, and geographic divisions within places. There may be more divisions within some of these domain categories. The customer base may be further divided according to priority and credits. The product may be further divided into categories, industries, and sectors.

Data that is essential to the functioning of a business is called Master Data. Entities including customers, products, suppliers, partners, workers, inventories, and so on are common ways to classify data. A term used to describe these groups is "Data Domains." [10][19]. Each of the domains may benefit from Master Data Management principles. Different

implementation issues arise in each of the areas. A Master Data Management system consists of two main parts:

- The resources necessary to profile, centralise, and synchronise the company's master data
- Applications for managing, cleaning, and enriching master data (both structured and unstructured).

III. MASTER DATA MANAGEMENT PHASES, TYPES AND APPROACHES

MDM ensures the accuracy and consistency of critical data by creating a unified, authoritative source. Key phases include identifying data sources, appointing data stewards, and designing infrastructure. Organisations can implement operational, analytic, or enterprise MDM solutions using approaches like consolidation or coexistence. Effective data governance with clear roles and collaboration between business and IT is essential. MDM improves efficiency, analytics, and decision-making.

A. Master Data Management Phases

A requirements analysis, priority setting, resource availability, time frame, and issue size analysis are all part of an MDM project plan. Most MDM initiatives, according to Roger Wolter of Microsoft Inc., include the following steps:

- Identify sources of master data.
- Figure out the consumers of the master data.
- Collect and analyse metadata for your master data.
- Appoint data stewards.
- Implement a data-governance program and data-governance council
- Develop the master data model.
- Choose a toolset.
- Design the infrastructure.
- Generate and test the master data.
- Modify the producing and consuming systems.
- Implement the maintenance processes.

B. Master Data Management Solution Types

MDM solutions often integrate with or are tightly linked to bigger programmes in most organisations. It may also extend across several applications. The three main types of MDM systems are:

1) Operational Master Data Management

- **Purpose:** Operational MDM focuses on managing and ensuring the quality and consistency of master data within operational applications and processes.
- **Key Functions:** It involves creating a single, authoritative source of master data that various operational systems can rely on. This ensures that data used across different applications (like CRM, ERP, etc.) is accurate and consistent in real time.
- **Benefits:** Improves operational efficiency, reduces errors due to inconsistent data, and enhances data quality across transactional systems.

2) Analytic Master Data Management

- **Purpose:** Analytic MDM focuses on integrating and managing master data across different analytical systems and data warehouses.
- **Key Functions:** It involves harmonising master data from various operational sources to provide a unified view for reporting, analytics, and business intelligence purposes.
- **Benefits:** Enables organisations to perform accurate and reliable analysis, reporting, and decision-making by ensuring that analytical systems use consistent and high-quality master data.

3) Enterprise Master Data Management

- **Purpose:** Enterprise MDM (EMDM) aims to provide a centralised and comprehensive approach to managing master data across an entire organisation.
- **Key Functions:** It integrates and governs master data across both operational and analytical domains, ensuring consistency and quality across the enterprise.
- **Benefits:** This is responsible for master data for the entire organisation, facilitates cross-functional sharing of data, guarantees certain conditions for the master data and can be useful for key decisions in the entire organisation.

IV. MASTER DATA MANAGEMENT STYLES IMPLEMENTATION

There is a wide range of options for storing and using master data. Each of the four approaches to implementing MDM has its own quirks that make it ideal for different types of businesses. These include things like cohabitation, registry, consolidation, and centralised. These methods provide different levels of centrally distributed master data governance and storage. Some are more disruptive or invasive than others when it comes to their effects on IT and business environments. Thus, everything relies on the several business requirements that entities have to fulfil in order to get a single view of their master data, including[20][21][22]:

- Improve security, stewardship, and data jurisdiction skills.
- Maximize the use and flexibility of current master data across all industries.
- Eliminate data silos across various systems and databases.
- The data of customers need to be centralised and connected.
- Facilitate upselling and cross-selling possibilities as part of an exceptional customer experience.
- Reduce operational and organisational expenses via improved decision-making and a better understanding of your company.

Master data management (MDM) system deployment success relies on implementation techniques. Their importance is paramount in the MDM system, regardless of whether you are constructing element-oriented structures or employing purchased software as a strategy. Master data management isn't easy to implement. Figure 2 displays the many approaches to data management.

Master Data Management Styles

Figure 2: Master Data Management Styles

- 1) **Style of Consolidation:** Usually, initiatives involving data warehousing or business intelligence (BI) employ them. We call this approach (MDM "downstream" since it occurs after operational systems have already generated master data.
- 2) **Registry Design:** For several source systems with different rules and architecture, which

makes determining information authority problematic, the registry MDM implementation option is optimal. The system gives each system a globally unique identification that may be used to match records and combine duplicates. As a result of real-time cataloguing of master data, it provides current views on commodities, customers, and other MDM sectors; nevertheless, indexing often causes delays. [9]

- 3) **Style of coexistence:** Style of coexistence the use of MDM results in the creation of a central data hub that relays updated records to their original sources. Companies whose operations depend on data replication or large-scale distribution strategies should adhere to this model.
- 4) **Centralized Design:** One or more MDM hubs are used for authoring, storing, and accessing master data in workflow or transaction use cases. The master data is created by the MDM and then centrally distributed to the other systems or applications. [8] This approach of MDM execution requires the most modifications to your application architecture and is most suited for highly controlled, top-down companies.

V. BENEFITS OF MDM INTEGRATION

Integration of MDM is a revolutionary approach that provides several advantages for businesses seeking to optimise the value of their data assets. This section discusses the several advantages of MDM integration as it affects data decision-making and organisational efficiency.

- **Better Data Quality:** MDM integration is a powerful tool capable of creating new veritable records of enhancing data quality within a company. Through consolidation, federation, or the coexistence model, organisations develop an authoritative source through master data.
- **Making Knowledgeable Decisions:** MDM integration is highly required in this context with the objective of allowing firm decision-making based on permitted data and information. Used in conjunction, master data could help clear some barriers and enable decision-makers to have complete picture of the pertinent facts.
- **Efficient Operation:** The perceived benefits of MDM integration across an organisation's operating environment are additional levels of efficiency. With centralised master data management, data governance is simplified, redundancies are eliminated, and the time and effort required for data upkeep are reduced.
- **Flexibility and Expandability:** The enhanced scalability and flexibility of MDM-integrated organisations makes them more capable of managing dynamic business conditions. As businesses grow and diversify, the ability to seamlessly integrate new data sources, adapt to changing business needs, and manage growing data formats becomes more crucial.

VI. EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR IMPLEMENTING MASTER DATA MANAGEMENT (MDM)

Organisations in the current digital era are having difficulty managing enormous volumes of data. Despite its merit, this data plague results in inaccuracies, repetitions, and inconsistencies that hinder decision-making and operational efficiency. MDM introduction turns into a fantastical fairytale. The honesty viewpoint, at the centre of MDM's existing resolution for master data pieces like customer goods and shareholder destinations, only continues to be significant

in this context. However, it's not always simple to implement an MDM's high-performance solution[23].

- **Define Your Goals and Scope:** Determining the goal or objectives is a necessary step before embarking on the MDM cruise. Which precise domains of data will be under control? Which operational efficiencies would you want to achieve, how will you enhance customer satisfaction, how will you increase regulatory compliance, or all three? It will be easier to implement what you want when its scope and goals are clearly defined, and they will also provide a foundation for evaluating how well it is implemented.
- **Build a Strong Governance Framework:** To guarantee that data are consistent, of high quality, and policy compliant, MDM need a robust governance architecture. Determining who owns what data, creating criteria for data quality, and basing operations on data stewardship protocols should all be part of this foundation. When disputes arise, data stewards step in as advocates for the data and help restore its integrity by resolving conflicting interests[24].
- **Choose the Right Technology Platform:** Selecting the right MDM technology platform is, in fact, essential to success. Scalability, integration possibilities, UI design, and service compatibility are other factors to take into account. Examine these leading MDM suppliers and carry out appropriate pilots to ensure that the specifications of the platform you have selected completely align with your budget, pricing policy, and unique requirements.
- **Data Quality is King:** Clean, accurate, and correspondingly impartial data is essential to MDM. Make sure that any missing values, redundancies, or inconsistencies are addressed via data enrichment and cleaning. Utilise data profiling technologies to identify and resolve problems related to low quality. The usual warning is applicable: you get what you pay for.
- **Embrace Change Management:** It is important to note that the adoption of MDM in an organisation is primarily a cultural change rather than a technical or technological endeavour. A major overhaul and strategic reactions are required during this transitional phase, but unsuccessful change management ignores this fact. In order to assure acceptance and avoid opposition, notify stakeholders of the potential advantages of MDM, guarantee that they will get enough training, and address any concerns.
- **Continuous Improvement is Key:** MDM is a lifelong process rather than something that occurs just once. Regularly assess the quality of your data, keep an eye on outcomes and accomplished objectives, and revise plans as they are being implemented. For this reason, embracing a culture of continuous development guarantees that your MDM system will remain relevant and provide value for a longer amount of time. and it has been providing value for years [6].

VII. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we undertake a comprehensive review of the current state of research on MDM, drawing on the information offered in the selected sources. The main objective is to get knowledge of various integration strategies, look into their benefits, and contrast them to find the most effective ones.

In, Kusuma Dewi, Fabrianti Kusumasari and Andreswari, (2019) focuses on creating new designs and evaluating current master data management architectures. Therefore, PT XYZ may use the architecture of the MDM tool design for open-

source systems. Reference and Master Data is one procedure used in data governance. Using an open-source platform, this method may serve as the basis for creating an MDM application[25].

In, Pansara et al. (2024) employ a comprehensive approach to explore how MDM's data governance aligns with Cybersecurity protocols to fortify against breaches. The methodology involves synthesising methodologies and best practices, proposing an integrated strategy. The paper concludes with adaptive strategies for navigating dynamic landscapes, serving as a foundational guide for harmonising MDM initiatives with robust Cybersecurity to fortify data assets against contemporary and emerging threats[26].

In, Haneem et al., (2017) provides an example of how descriptive analysis and text analysis may be used to accomplish a common goal of SLR, which is to examine the development of a certain research topic. There is evidence that these methods can synthesise the developments in the field of MDM. This research found a pattern in the distribution of comparable literary works by year, source, and publishing type using descriptive analysis[27].

In, Liu et al., (2020) the traits of the master data are used to determine the identifying indicators. When building the system for identifying master data, the weight of the indicators is determined by their relative value to the company. After compiling the findings of the data survey and census, the next step is to establish a solid groundwork for future data governance by identifying the master data and clarifying the extent of master data characteristics. Lastly, construct the business owner master data model[28].

In, Vilminko-Heikkinen and Pekkola, (2013) drawn from a year-long MDM project, which helps us determine the processes and interdependencies that need to be considered while implementing MDM services within an organisation. Along with the little MDM literature, these phases and their dependencies, along with other incidental concerns, assist organisations in developing MDM functions [29].

A. Research gaps

Despite the significant advancements in Master Data Management (MDM) architectures, several gaps remain in the literature, particularly concerning the design of MDM tools for open-source systems applicable to specific organisational contexts. While existing studies have explored various facets of MDM, including data governance, cybersecurity alignment, and the use of descriptive analysis to map research progress, there is a notable lack of integrated frameworks that cater specifically to open-source environments. Furthermore, while methodologies for identifying master data and establishing MDM functions have been discussed, there is limited focus on adaptive, scalable solutions that align with dynamic organisational needs and emerging cybersecurity threats. Addressing these gaps would significantly contribute to the development of robust, flexible, and secure MDM architectures tailored to the evolving demands of organisations utilising open-source platforms.

VIII. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A vast array of literature that has been gathered from many sources has examined MDM. After that, a single real-world case study was examined. It demonstrates how using the MDM solution from start to finish has assisted the organisation in regaining its composure. We now provide an overview of the industry executives' interviews. We had in-person interactions with them using a questionnaire that we had produced. Since master data, such as customer, product, and staff information, is the primary use case for the MDM system. Thus, we used TDWI data that was gathered from 741 respondents across various firms to get an understanding of pertinent master data. We interpret the survey's credibility as

having been sponsored and participated in by industry giants such as Informatica, Business Objects, Teradata, and Actuate. Figure 3 presents the survey results, which were derived from 2,982 answers provided by 741 participants.

Figure 3: Findings of the survey Based on 2,982 responses from 741 respondents.

Figure 4. Based on 741 respondents.

The Figure 4 shows Based on 741 respondents and Table 1 shows the summary of Interviewees' organisation.

Table 1: Summary of Interviewees' Organization.

Company	Business Area	Geography	Role
A	Healthcare	Asia Pacific	R&D Scientist
B	Retail	India	Business Analyst
C	IT	USA, Europe, Asia Pacific	Practice Manager

IX. RESULTS

The interview was conducted in a cordial manner throughout our interactions with the company leaders. Their recorded answers to the questionnaire make it a really intriguing read. In the conversion, Manager "A" was amiable and demonstrated his acute listening skills. He was responding with "Not clear" if he wasn't sure about anything. Manager B was responding to our questions with great enthusiasm. Being a tech enthusiast, Manager C is well-versed in the causes of the issues. The interview excerpts are provided under Table 2:

Table 2: Interviewees' responses to challenges.

Challenges faced by A	Applications use various meanings of data. The disparate formats of the data make integration and standardisation difficult. The ownership of data is not properly enforced. Errors are caused by data transport. Application integration is time-consuming. Not all fields are transferred when merging from different sources. All parties involved in the change management process are confused, including the ETL team and the MDM staff. Duplicate CDI hubs are present.
Challenges faced by B	Data volume is growing quickly, necessitating improvements in data quality. Inadequate definition of master data leads to misunderstandings. Not a single data model. Keeping up with data is a difficult task. No standardised procedure exists for updating data. Lack of data ownership. The integration

	procedure is difficult due to several CDI systems. Integrity of attributes is lost during integration.
Challenges faced by C	A appropriate format is not used for older data. It's hard to define master data. Consolidating data is a difficult task. There is no established data maintenance procedure. Certain apps have very challenging interface development. It is unusual to utilise certain data and data models. Data transfer requires a lot of time. Absence of a single, shared identity. No shared object technique. It is impossible to determine which iteration of the client profile is correct.

MDM is still in its infancy as a concept thus there is more work to be done in this area. The effort has received substantial funding from management, who saw the significance of MDM and emphasised it. Their certainty over the ROI, nevertheless, is unwavering. The conversation was on MDM, but they seemed to be talking about data management more generally, which includes CRM and data warehouse.

The interviews showed that there are a few similar difficulties that almost all organisations encounter. The issue of poor data quality was brought up by everyone. It is the source of all significant issues, according to them. Data ownership model is impacted by this. Understanding the business climate and company model was their first priority.

X. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The difficulties associated with master data customers have been researched. The analysis makes it evident that the existence of redundant CDIs, data and application integration, data consolidation, issues with data governance, and metadata management are the primary obstacles. Since MDM involves using technology, we also learned that business activities are necessary in the MDM space to address issues that transcend beyond technology. Master Data Management (MDM) stands as a critical pillar in modern manufacturing operations, offering substantial benefits in data quality enhancement, operational efficiency, and decision-making accuracy. By establishing a unified and authoritative source for master data, organisations can streamline processes, reduce errors, and foster greater collaboration across departments. The review of MDM implementation styles—consolidation, registry, centralised, and coexistence—illustrates varied approaches to managing and governing master data, each suited to specific organisational contexts and requirements. However, challenges such as data quality issues, integration complexities, and the need for robust governance frameworks persist, underscoring the ongoing evolution and refinement of MDM practices. Future research should focus on advancing open-source MDM solutions, enhancing cybersecurity integration, and optimising MDM frameworks for scalability and adaptability in dynamic business environments.

For future work, continuous improvement in data quality, expansion of MDM scope to include emerging data types like IoT data, and enhancing integration capabilities across supply chain partners are crucial. Additionally, leveraging advanced analytics and machine learning for predictive insights and real-time decision support can further enhance the value derived from MDM initiatives in manufacturing.

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